

Social Impact Assessment (SIA) Analysis Framework

WHAT IS AN SIA FRAMEWORK

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About The Booklet

Introduction to SIA framework

Embedding place-based equity, social inclusion, and participatory governance in Industrial Urban Symbiosis (IUS) demonstration.

A model where circular economy solutions are co-developed, assessed, and legitimised through the active involvement of communities they aim to serve.

Framework Summary

The Social Impact Assessment (SIA) Framework provides a structured methodology for evaluating and enhancing the social dimensions of circular economy transitions through IUS networks.

In the case of the United Circles Project, three European demonstrators aim to move towards a more circular production system in different areas. Each of these demonstrators will be integrated into a 'Regional Circularity Hub' (knowledge and development hub), which will help urban-industrial management and evolution by incorporating financing methods, digital tools and social innovation to make this waste reduction a reality.

Actions across each hub:

- In **Spain**, a wastewater treatment plant will become a resource recovery centre by obtaining nutrients, energy and cellulose in an integrated way.
- In **Italy**, food waste in the form of used cooking oil will be recovered in a biorefinery to create new bioplastic products.
- In **Turkey**, construction and demolition waste from the region will be transformed into a new two-storey 3D printed building using low-carbon recycled materials.

These IUS hubs will be expanded over time in a process of duplication and extension to other countries: Hungary, South Africa, Greece and the United Kingdom, in what are called 'mirror demonstrators'. Slovenia, Lebanon, Austria and France, will promote the possibility of forming 'seed demonstrators' to help develop a network of stakeholders to gain investment to start up the 'Regional Circularity Hub'.

The SIA ensures that Hubs for Circularity (H4C) create equitable benefits whilst avoiding negative impacts on communities.

The framework focuses on three key impact dimensions:

Employment

Job creation and quality

Equitability

Fair access to benefits

Equality

Inclusion of marginalised groups

It uses a double materiality lens to examine both how IUS activities affect communities and how social factors influence hub success.

Also built on Territorial Social Responsibility (TSR) principles, the framework adapts to different governance models and provides practical tools for stakeholder engagement, data collection, and impact measurement. It aligns with European standards including European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) and integrates with digital platforms like the GRETA sustainability assessment tool.

Main Components of the SIA Framework

01 Assessment Objectives

The framework provides H4C facilitators with a structured methodology to evaluate and enhance social dimensions of circular economy transitions:

- **Evaluate Impact Distribution:** Systematically assesses how IUS initiatives affect different social groups, ensuring equitable distribution of benefits and burdens
- **Ensure Equitable Outcomes:** Focuses on fair distribution of environmental improvements across all community segments, with particular attention to historically marginalised groups
- **Integrate Multiple Dimensions:** Incorporates environmental, economic, and social dimensions, recognising that sustainable transitions require both technical innovation and social transformation

02 Key Impact Dimensions

Employment

Examines job quality, creation patterns, and skills transition pathways. Quantifies job creation in circular sectors, assesses working conditions, and measures demographic distribution of employment benefits.

Equitability

Addresses fair access to benefits, services, and decision-making processes. Evaluates how environmental improvements benefit different groups and identifies potential unintended consequences.

Equality

Focuses on representation of disadvantaged groups and environmental justice. Ensures less vocal communities are empowered within IUS networks and examines fair distribution of benefits and burdens.

03 Double Materiality Lens

Examines impact in both directions between IUS initiatives and society:

This perspective is implemented across all assessment stages, connecting social impact metrics with economic sustainability indicators.

04 Territorial Social Responsibility (TSR) Axes

Assessment activities are organised across five interconnected responsibility axes: Community, Environmental, Economy, Politics and Institutions

Territorial Social Responsibility in UNITED CIRCLES

Localised Socio-Environmental Accountability

Linking IUS Initiatives with the lived experiences of local communities

Integration with Regional Policy and Finance Systems

Embedding social responsibility within financing models and policy roadmaps

Support for just Transition Policies

Ensuring no one is left behind as IUS hubs undergo transformation

Community-Led Social Change

Co-designing circular solutions through participatory activities

Equity and Inclusiveness as Core Principles

Integrating gender, minority and youth inclusion within circularity initiatives

Data-Driven Social Impact Monitoring

Embedding socio-environmental metrics at city and regional levels

05 Implementation Process

The assessment process is mapped to a hub's lifecycle stages:

- **Planning Phase:** Stakeholder identification, baseline data collection, and framework customisation before implementation begins
- **Implementation and Data Collection Phase:** Ongoing monitoring through surveys, interviews, participatory methods, and environmental monitoring
- **Analysis and Reporting Phase:** Regular assessment cycles using double materiality lens, supporting transparency and community accountability

06 Critical Assessment Questions

Tailored questions guide the assessment process across four key areas:

- **Understanding Context:** What constitutes a “healthier environment”? Who lives and works in assessment areas? What are existing environmental conditions?
- **Impact Assessment:** How might IUS activities affect stakeholder groups? What are employment impacts? How are benefits and burdens distributed?
- **Community Engagement:** What solutions do community members propose? How can interests be aligned? What governance mechanisms ensure participation?
- **Risk Management:** What unintended consequences might occur? How can negative impacts be minimised whilst maximising benefits?

07 Theory of Change

The United Circles framework outlines a comprehensive approach to assessing the social impacts of IUS networks. This framework focuses on creating equitable, inclusive, and sustainable transitions to a circular economy, by incorporating community-driven approaches, integrating social impact indicators, and emphasizing continuous learning and engagement.

Continous engagement, adaptation and stakeholder engagement are crucial for successful implementation and long-term sustainability of the SIA

This Theory of Change articulates causal pathways linking IUS activities to social impacts:

Activity-Output Links: How IUS activities generate measurable outputs including materials processed, jobs created, and stakeholder participation

Output-Outcome Pathways: How outputs contribute to improved environmental quality, enhanced skills, strengthened networks, and better health

Outcome-Impact Relationships: How intermediate outcomes create long-term impacts including healthier communities, resilient economies, and enhanced social cohesion

Feedback Loops: How social impacts influence enabling conditions for further IUS development

08 Governance Models

Provides differentiated strategies for six H4C governance structures:

Association without Legal Entity: Distributed responsibilities, shared platforms for collaborative assessment

Legal Entity within Regional Government: Alignment with regional frameworks, leveraging public data sources

Private Non-Profit Legal Entity: Demonstrating social return on investment, balancing economic and social metrics

Dual Governance Approach: Clear delineation of responsibilities between infrastructure and innovation entities

Business Company with Public-Private Partners: Addressing diverse stakeholder priorities, aligning with board vision

Coalition of Large Industrial Companies: Industry specific metrics, corporate sustainability reporting integration

09 Templates and Tools

Comprehensive practical resources include:

Stakeholder Mapping Tools: Identify stakeholders, assess interests and influence, plan engagement strategies

Data Collection Plans: Guide quantitative and qualitative data collection through multiple methods

Analysis Frameworks: Support systematic interpretation using mixed methods, triangulation, and validity checks

Monitoring and Evaluation Tools: Track progress, identify issues, support adaptive management

Digital Integration: GRETA tool compatibility, H4C network platforms, hub checklists for easy data exchange

10 Ethical and Quality Assurance

Robust standards throughout all activities:

- **Gender-Responsive Approach:** Examine differential impacts, ensure 40% minimum women's representation, pursue gender empowerment
- **Transparency and Accessibility:** Clear communication, accessible processes, language support, alternative formats
- **Participatory Quality Control:** Peer review by experts and community representatives, structured community feedback opportunities
- **Data Protection and Ethics:** GDPR compliance, community data ownership protocols, explicit consent processes
- **Methodological Integrity:** Due process oversight, regular review, transparent reporting, clear escalation procedures

11 External Alignment

Aligned with established European and international standards:

European : ESRS requirements, Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive compliance, EU Green Deal alignment

International Standards: UNEP Social LifeCycle Assessment guidelines, ISO 26000 social responsibility guidance, UN SDGs alignment

Regional Integration: Zero-Pollution Performance Scoreboard alignment, standardised pollution indicators

Digital Integration: GRETA tool compatibility, H4C network platforms, comprehensive impact evaluation capability

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